

Mediation Role of Coordination over Supervision and Communication: A Study of Indian Construction Companies

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Abstract: The intent of this research study is to understand the essence of relationship among communication, coordination and supervision variable. To carry out this study communication is considered as an independent variable (I.V.), coordination is considered as a mediating variable (M.V.) and supervision is considered as a dependent variable (D.V.). Post data analysis and from output, it is concluded that a) there is a strong relationship between I.V. and D.V., b) there is a relationship between M.V and D.V., c) there is a mediation effect of M.V. over the relationship of I.V and D.V.

Keywords: Construction, Real estate, Mediation model, Supervision, Communication, Coordination

JEL Classification Number: J74, M12, M54, O15

1. Introduction

The construction and development of real estate building projects are either initiated by government through contracting system or by builder, promoters themselves. Socio-cultural differences among regions, differences in technical execution skill/s across the construction industries may lead to disagreement among employees, hence yet times it may motivate the employees to quit the job. Employees are expected to demonstrate a skill set of unified communication, coordination and supervision which are interdependent. Universities and technical institutes are playing a major role in imparting the knowledge at technical training, diploma, graduation, post-graduation level. While discharging one's duties, employees are required to communicate, coordinate and supervise in achieving the project goals. Foremen dedicated for a task-oriented job; engineers at various hierarchical levels supervise more than one job, hence it is required to communicate, coordinate and supervise among jobs/departamental/stake holders. Migrated employees (all levels and cadre) may require to have effective communication, coordination and supervision skills, but which is always challenging one. The harmony among the employees may lead to sustainable environment.

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This study is designed to study the influence of communication (I.V.) over supervision (D.V.), to observe the influence of coordination (M.V.) over the supervision (D.V.) and to observe coordination (M.V.) effect over the communication (I.V.) and supervision (D.V.) relationship.

2. Literature Review

The engineer monitoring the work required to supervise, communicate, and coordinate. The work required to discharge is being tedious employee may experience fatigue. In the trial of achieving planned quantity and quality, engineer has to monitor closely the work progress through supervision, supervision is merely guiding the team in attaining the set goal or targets. Supervising engineer should possess the capabilities of issuing orders, instructions, planning, organizing the works; assigning the tasks; team motivation; issuing workers report of work performance; bridging the requirement of employers with team. Supervising engineer should possess a skill set of tact of discretion capability; technical competency; social skills; honesty; empathy; courage; communication skills; self-confidence; coordination, teaching, guidance and powerful common sense. Investors/developers/ contractors engaging the specialists in order to maximize the quality output, profits, save time. Hence, the engineers are required to coordinate, communicate, supervise all those specialists engaged at work.

Communication is a soft skill and primarily meant to exchange the data, information in any aspect with respect to a project job/task. The engineer has to communicate in the interest of product deliverables, proper communication is highly appreciable. Neville Stanton Alan et al., (2005) has concluded that construction project stakeholders are owners, designers, architects, contractors, vendors, billing engineers and unmentioned stake holders, and they required to go hand-in-hand in achieving common goals. Mosier and Chidester (1991), Bowers et al. (1998b) and Alan et al. (2005) have expressed that closed loop communication is essential to cling to the schedules, quality as well as quantity. Communication among all stake holders expected during prior to award, during award and post award of the contract. During the project execution communication among stake holders is essential in addressing the clarification/issues/ambiguities. The communication failure may be observed as information not communicated, wrong information communicated, information communication is incomplete.

Kasimu and Usman (2013) has concluded that Ineffective communication system leads to de-motivated workforce, design errors, slowdown in the entire job and failure in production. Axley (1984) has concluded that communication shall be a pipeline that transfers information from one individual to another. Leje et al. (2019) has concluded that

to achieve better organizational performance, it is preferred to adhere to the effective communication tools and instruments.

As per the study of Rahman and Gami (2019) the ineffective and inefficient communication will result high stress in work place. Pocock et al. (1996) has concluded that designers and contractor interaction resulted enhanced cost and schedule performance, but the same is not true with project performance beyond a certain degree of interaction. Thomas et al. (1998) indicated that 41% of successful projects resulted from effective communication. The flow of communication within an organization has been depicted in Figure 1 and the supervisor’s flow of communication depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 1: Flow of communication in an organization (Source: Author)

Meding and Bruenei (2010) have concluded that communication commitment is making an impact on supervision, which leads to poor quality attainment. Berenger et al. (2016) have concluded that communication problems have been witnessed in construction projects and that leads to waste of time. Aiyewalehinmi (2013) has concluded that work place communication in attaining the common goal is very important and a survey for communication has been carried considering the stake holders of construction industry (i.e. employees, management, unions) and found that employees’ perceptions of workplace communication were 72.5%, Union 91.2% and management 60.9% of total variance obtained from all social parties. Jimoh et al. (2017) have concluded the communication has stood in the rank wise.

Malone and Crowston (1990) have defined Coordination as “the process of managing dependencies among activities and linking together different parts to accomplish a collective set of tasks”. Lengel (1989) and Forrester (1999) have expressed coordination from the perspective of supervising engineer is to meet tasks requirement and also expressed that less or excess coordination may impede project performance due to waste

or lack of information. Shen and Chang (2013) in their article concluded that coordination time or amount should be adjusted in accordance with coordination supply.

Figure 2: Supervisor’s communication with other stake holders

Source: Author’s depiction.

Wang (2000) has concluded that coordination is one of the root causes for project failure. Jha and Misra (2007) mentioned that project coordination shall be addressed through resource handling, planning, team building and contract implementation coordination activities. Alaloul et al. (2015) have found Scheduling (RII = 0.97), Quality assurance plan (RII = 0.93), and all parties’ participation in plans (RII = 0.89) are most effective coordination factors as per relative importance index (RII). The coordination categories exhibited in Figure3 and relationships between coordination needs and methods has been exhibited in Figure 4.

Figure 3: Coordination Categories (Chang 2001; Chang, Shen 2009)

Figure 4: Relationships between coordination needs and methods (Chang 2001; Chang, Shen 2009)

Ming-Sum (2005) has described supervision as a means to enhance staff development, and helps to equip the workers with the professional knowledge and skills necessary to do their job effectively, also gives workers the opportunity to communicate, coordinate, and cooperate with one another as a team. Jimoh et al. (2017) has expressed supervision is a key variable and depends on various factors. Chika and Chijioke (2013) have expressed that some supervisors are not qualified to supervise and those that are qualified and experienced to supervise find the supervisees difficult to supervise because of their attitudes. These make the supervisors to often be driven to a state of defeat and despair leading to the failure of construction works.

The similar kind of study has been not carried out in Hyderabad, India to best knowledge of the author, hence this work will fulfil the requirement of interdependency of the mentioned variables and its importance in the construction industry.

4. Methodology

The flow of study has been initiated with a literature review, capturing variable, preparation of questionnaire instrument and then to conduct pilot study, questionnaire instrument editing, administering the final survey, redundant data elimination and finally analysis of data using statistical package for the social sciences (S.P.S.S), summarization of findings and conclusion remarks. See the Figure 5.

Figure 5: Study Methodology

Source: Authors.

4.1. Population parameter and sample size

Civil engineers from southern part of Hyderabad, India, have been considered as population and sample is considered from construction companies from Hyderabad. Random sampling methodology has been adopted for collecting the sample. Sample size is considered as 150.

4.2. Variables

Communication is considered as an independent variable (I.V), coordination is considered as a mediating variable (M.V) and supervision is considered as a dependent variable (D.V.).

4.3. Source of Data

The study is being unique in nature and due to none availability of data, the data was supposed to be collected directly from respondents. Hence, collected data shall be treated as primary data.

4.4. Questionnaire Preparation

A questionnaire constructed considering five variables/factors namely supervision, coordination, communication and fatigue. A closed ended questionnaire is constructed and 1- 5 Likert's scale has been engaged (i.e., strongly disagree to strongly agree) to have the collect responses.

4.5. Pilot Study

The questionnaire has been circulated in civil engineers' community and forty responses has been received. Data has been tested for correlation over S.P.S.S software package and Karl Pearson's coefficient of correlation two tailed significance and flag significant correlation test has resulted Pearson critical coefficient is as 0.312 at 5% significance. Correlation test indicates that 25 variables found correlated out of 54 variables; communication, coordination, supervision correlated, whereas fatigue factor not correlated, hence non-correlated factor/sub-factors have been eliminated from the questionnaire. Twenty-nine sub factors/variables have been eliminated and four factors, 25 variables have been considered for further study.

4.6 Mediation model

Mediation referred to be as the transmission of the effect of an I.V. on a D.V. through one or more variable. This model shall be called as single mediator variable. The mediation shall be known as partial mediation if the I.V. has both direct and indirect effect on D.V. and shall be called as full mediation if the I.V. effect observed indirect effect. The proposed mediation model has been depicted as path model (Fig 6). It is to understand that whether there is a direct relationship between I.V. and D.V as well as to explore the influence of M.V. over the relation of I.V and D.V.

4.7. Final study

The finalized questionnaire instrument has been circulated among civil engineers in request to participate and targeted to middle sized contracting firm/promoters/ builders in Hyderabad, southern part of India. One hundred fifty-four (154) responses received from working civil engineering community over a time period of four months duration and one hundred fifty (150) responses found fit for analysis, hence it is considered for data analysis.

4.8. Data analysis

To test the relationship among variables as well as influence of one variable over the relationship of the other two variables, linear regression analysis applied using S.P.S.S package. Communication variable has been considered as independent variable (I.V), coordination variable has been considered as mediating variable (M.V.) and supervision variable as dependent variable (D.V). The proposed Mediation model has been demonstrated in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Proposed Path diagram

Source: Author.

4.9. Findings and Conclusion

The summary of findings and conclusion will be carried out based on analysis outcome.

4.10. Limitation

The study has been limited to private developers, contractors, builder of construction industry in Hyderabad, India and these agencies are involved in developing residential infrastructure in Hyderabad, India.

4.11. Hypotheses

The formulated hypotheses for the proposed study are as follows:

4.11.1 Hypotheses-1

H₀: There is no-significant relation between communication (i.e., I.V.) and supervision (i.e. D.V.).

H₁: There is a significant relation between communication (i.e., I.V.) and supervision (i.e. D.V.).

4.11.2. Hypotheses - 2

H₀: There is no-significant relation between communication (i.e., I.V.), coordination (i.e. M.V.).

H₁: There is a significant relation between communication (i.e., I.V.), coordination (i.e. M.V.).

4.11.3. Hypotheses - 3

H₀: There is no-significant relation between coordination (i.e., M.V.) with supervision (i.e. D.V.).

H₁: There is a significant relation between coordination (i.e., M.V.) with supervision (i.e. D.V.).

4.11.4. Hypotheses - 4

H₀: There is no-mediation effect of coordination (M.V.) over communication (I.V.) and supervision (D.V.) relation.

H₁: There is full mediation effect of coordination (M.V.) over communication (I.V.) and supervision (D.V.) relation.

5. Data analysis

The data has been compiled in Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) and follows as:

5.1. Descriptive statistics of demographics:

The responses of demographics have been analysed and tabulated in a Table 1:

Table 1: Statistics of Demographics

Demography	Statistics
Gender	4% are of female; 96% are of male
Marital status	28% are of married; 108% are of unmarried
Age (years)	21 to 24 (34%); 24-31 (36%); 31 to 38 (12%); 38-45 (14%); more than 45 (4%)
Educational qualification	Civil engineers: Graduated (66%); Post graduated (34%)
Work experience (years)	0 to 1 (10%); 1 to 2 (38%), 2 to 4 (12%); 4 to 6 (4%); 6 to 9 (6%); 9 to 15 (12%); more than 15 (18%)
Salary (INR)	0/- to 10,000/- (4%); 10,000/- to 14,000/- (18%); 14,000/- to 18,000/- (14%); Rs. 18,000/- to 25,000/- (14%); Rs. 25,000/- to 35,000/- (10%); Rs. 35,000/- to 45,000/- (2%); more than Rs. 55,000/- (28%).
Residence	rented (24%); ancestors (12%); owned (26%); company guest house (38%)
Family association	joint families (8%); nucleus families (135%); Away from family (7%)

5.2. Analysis of data

The responses have been summarized and loaded on to SPSS, then the data has been analysed by operating linear regression tool.

Communication (I.V.) and Supervision (D.V.) data analysed by linear regression engaging the SPSS and the analysis is:

A significant regression equation was found ($F(1,148) = 2278.492, p < 0.00$) with an R^2 of 0.939. Supervisor = - 0.202 + 0.862 * Communication

Communication (I.V.) and Coordination (M.V.) data analysed by linear regression engaging the SPSS and the analysis is:

A significant regression equation was found ($F(1,148) = 275.152, p < 0.00$) with an R^2 of 0.650. $Coordination = 0.801 + 0.686 * Communication + 0.592$

Coordination (M.V.) and Supervision (D.V.) data analyzed by linear regression engaging the SPSS and the analysis is:

A significant regression equation was found ($F(1,148) = 118.67, p < 0.00$) with an R^2 of 0.445. $Supervision = -0.754 + 0.986 * Coordination + 0.745$

Communication (I.V.), Coordination (M.V.) and Supervision (D.V.) data analyzed by linear regression engaging the SPSS and the analysis is:

A significant regression equation was found ($F(2,147) = 1182.083, p < 0.00$) with an R^2 of 0.941. $Coordination = -0.272 + 0.802 * Communication + 0.088 * Coordination + 0.242$

6. Findings and Conclusion

The findings and conclusion are summarized as per the objective(s).

6.1. Objective 2.1: To study the influence of I.V. over D.V.

From hypotheses testing, I am unable to accept the null hypotheses, hence null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis has been accepted. It is concluded that there is a statistically significant influence of communication (i.e. I.V.) over the supervision (i.e. D.V.). From the testing outcome it is very clear to mention that communication variable is one of the supervising characters. From the linear regression, the total effect (C) between communication and supervision is worked out as 0.862.

Figure 7: Total Effect between I.V. and D.V

6.2. Objective 2.2: To observe the influence of M.V. over the D.V.

From hypotheses testing, I am unable to accept the null hypotheses, hence null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis has been accepted. It is concluded that there is a statistically significant influence of coordination (i.e., M.V.) over the supervision (i.e., D.V.). From the testing outcome it is very clear to mention that coordination variable is one of the supervising characters.

6.3. Objective 2.3: To observe M.V. effect over the I.V and D.V. relationship

From hypotheses testing, this research is unable to accept the null hypotheses, hence null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis has been accepted. It is concluded that there is a statistically significant influence of coordination (i.e. M.V.) over the communication (I.V.) and supervision (i.e. D.V.) relationship. From the testing outcome it is very clear to mention that coordination is influencing the communication and supervision relationship.

From the linear regression analysis, the unstandardized coefficient of communication and coordination is (B) 0.686 and the standard error is 0.041. The unstandardized coefficients of coordination and supervision (i.e. a) is (B) 0.088 and the standard error is 0.35. The unstandardized coefficients of coordination and supervision (i.e. Direct effect) is (B) 0.802 and the standard error is 0.03.

Figure 8: Total Effect between I.V. and D.V

$$\begin{aligned}
 C \text{ (Total effect)} &= \text{Direct effect} + \text{Indirect effect} \\
 &= C^1 + a * b \\
 &= 0.802 + (0.686) * (0.088) = 0.862
 \end{aligned}$$

From the above relationship it is concluded that there is a partial mediation among the communication (I.V.), supervision (i.e. D.V.) and coordination (i.e. M.V.). Sobel testing concludes that there is a significant mediation effect (p= 0.01290538) among mentioned variables.

The outcome of communication is in line with Thomas et al. (1998), Rahman and Gami (2019), opinion of communication, but Pocock et al. have mentioned it true to certain extent and not true beyond a certain degree of interaction. The outcome of coordination is in line with Shen and Chang (2013), Wang et al. (2007).

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